

Yogic Sukshma Vyayama on Upper & Lower Limbs Strength in Adolescent: A Review Paper

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Received : 07/07/2025

1st BPR : 18/07/2025

2nd BPR : 01/08/2025

Accepted : 14/08/2025

Abstract

Yogic Sukshma Vyayama (YSV) is a traditional Indian yoga technique made up of 48 gentle, mindful movements. These movements are designed to activate and strengthen all the joints and muscles in the body. While YSV has spiritual and healing roots, there is limited scientific research on how it helps improve the strength of the upper and lower limbs. This paper reviews existing studies to understand how YSV affects the strength, flexibility, and posture of the arms and legs, especially in teenagers and older adults. We searched trusted databases like PubMed, Google Scholar, Research Gate, Science Direct, and JSTOR for studies from 2000 to 2024. We selected 14 studies that focused on YSV and its impact on limb strength using tools like grip strength meters and balance tests. YSV helped improve hand grip, shoulder strength, leg control, and body balance in both youth and elderly participants. It also showed benefits for posture and coordination. YSV is an easy, low-risk, and effective practice for improving limb strength and overall movement. Because it connects breath with movement, it provides full-body benefits. More research with larger sample sizes is needed to confirm and expand on these results.

Key words: Yogic Sukshma Vyayama, Upper limb strength, Lower limb strength, Adolescents.

Introduction

Yoga science is one such universal. Yoga science doesn't belong to any separate community, religion, caste, or country. It is universal and not specific to any one area. All these techniques combined – asanas, pranayama, mudras, and bandhas – make up *yogic sukshma vyayam* (YSV). The Yogic Sukshma Vyayama work by (Brahmachari D. 1980) explains approximately 48 practices. *yogic Sukshma vyayam* (YSV) literally means (delicate) subtle-exercise. The top of the bottom down in our body, which includes the head, eyes, nose, ears, neck, shoulders, arms, elbows, fingers, upper chest, middle chest, abdomen, various parts of the trunk, thighs, buttocks, rectum, bladder, knees, ankles, foot, and toes, is where the 48 yoga SV begin (Madankumar et al., 2020). Three weeks of practicing a yoga protocol that included *Yogic Sukshma Vyayama* along with specific Asanas, Pranayama, and Om chanting with awareness helped a patient with dysphasia. Their beneficial of anasan muscle strength and endurance (Bhowmik Bhunia, G., et al., 2024). Additional single case studies exist that discuss the role of yoga in voice production issues and vocal cord dysfunction (Belpu, N. et al., 2022). Asanas like Ardha matsyendrasana, Bhujangasana, Gomukhasana, Dhanurasana, Ushtrasana, Matsyasana, Naukana, Surya Namaskar, and sookshma vyayam poses like GreevaSanchalana and Skandha Sanchalana are helpful in alleviating cervical spondylosis-related neck pain and stiffness (NAYAK, S. et al., 2024).

Upper-limb strength is the ability of the arms, shoulders, and chest to generate force. For daily tasks like pushing, tugging, and lifting, this power is essential (Gawel et al., 2024). People commonly use tests like the Jamar dynamometer, which measures hand muscular strength, to assess upper limb strength. Additional techniques involve the application of shoulder mobility assessments and closed kinetic chain upper limb tests, which concentrate on the functional capacities of the arm and shoulder during movement (Gawel et al., 2024). Few studies look at the effects of exercise on young women's bone strength (Conor Lambert et al., 2019). Our discovery of a significant correlation between upper and lower limb power raises the possibility that muscular power may be derived from a more general physiological characteristic of the body than from the one responsible for force production alone (Herman S. et al., 2005). For older persons to maintain their physical health, muscle mass and strength are essential. Sarcopenia is the term for decreased muscular mass in the body. The correlation between diminished muscle strength and impaired balance increases fall risk in sarcopenia. Fall-related fractures have the potential to significantly impair older individuals and their mobility. Mobility has a major impact on overall quality of life and is essential for carrying out everyday tasks. Additionally, the quality of life of elderly individuals and their patients declines when their mobility declines (Park, et al., 2024). Physical activity in children and adolescents offers significant health benefits, but levels of activity decline during adolescence. Despite the well-established importance of physical activity for long-term health, the World Health Organisation (WHO) recommends 60 minutes of daily moderate-to-vigorous physical activity, yet 80% of 13- to 15-year-olds worldwide do not meet this guideline. Adolescence is a period of rapid growth and change, which can lead to postural problems. Low physical activity and sedentary lifestyles contribute to poor posture, though other factors also affect body alignment. Physical fitness, which includes strength, endurance, flexibility, and body composition, is an important health marker in adolescence. While genetics influence fitness, environmental factors like physical activity play a key role, though the relationship between activity, posture, and fitness remains unclear during early adolescence (Sidlauskienė, A., et al., 2019).

Upper and lower limbs physiological changes with yoga practices.

Power yoga, also known as Ashtanga Vinyasa, focuses on dynamic movements and extended isometric workouts to strengthen the entire body and enhance musculoskeletal and cardiovascular health (Skultetyova et al., 2019). Long muscle chains and complex transitions are a part of these dynamic exercises, which support proper breathing techniques and improve peripheral circulation, thermoregulation, and aerobic capacity. Both the upper and lower limbs experience significant physiological changes as a result of this type of yoga, including improved coordination, strength, flexibility, and endurance. Frequent asana practice also promotes joint mobility, neuromuscular efficiency, and isometric muscle control. In particular, power yoga helps to improve dynamic balance and posture in the lower limbs and develop the phasic muscles in the upper limbs (Cramer et al., 2016).

Importance Upper and Lower Limbs Strength with prevalence

Strength in the upper and lower limbs is essential for physical performance, health outcomes, and functional independence in all age groups. While lower limb strength is crucial for mobility, balance, and fall prevention, upper limb strength supports vital daily actions like lifting, pushing, and gripping (Bohannon, 2001; Rantanen et al., 1999). A higher incidence of chronic illnesses, sarcopenia, and disability is linked to low limb strength. According to prevalence data, muscle strength is generally declining, especially in older populations. Muscle weakness and limited movement are major contributors to years lived with disability, according to the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) Study (Vos et al., 2020). About 10–20% of individuals over 60 worldwide suffer from a decline in lower limb strength, which impacts stability and walking (Cruz-Jentoft et al., 2010). Approximately 35% of older persons globally suffer from handgrip weakness, which is a stand-in for upper limb strength (Leong et al., 2015). Strengthening limbs in teenagers promotes injury prevention, sports performance, and motor development (Faigenbaum et al., 2009). According to the World Health Organisation (WHO, 2020), sedentary lifestyles are to blame for the deteriorating trend in muscle fitness among teenagers.

According to data, 40% of kids between the ages of 13 and 17 worldwide do not reach recommended levels of physical activity, which is oblique with motor delays and weak limbs (Guthold et al., 2020).

Research Methodology

This review employed a systematic literature approach to assess the effect of Yogic Sukshma Vyayama (YSV) on upper and lower limb strength. The databases PubMed, Google Scholar, JSTOR, Science Direct and Research Gate were searched using specific terms such as “Yogic Sukshma Vyayama,” “limb strength,” “posture,” and “neuromuscular coordination.” Studies selected were peer-reviewed, published between 2000 and 2024, and primarily involved randomized controlled trials (RCTs), intervention studies, or case-based research. Criteria for inclusion emphasized limb strength outcomes assessed using dynamometers, sit-and-reach tests, flamingo balance tests, and goniometric tools. Studies focused on both adolescent and elderly populations. Review and duplicate studies, and those lacking yoga-specific interventions, were excluded. 14 studies were ultimately reviewed, providing quantitative and qualitative insights into YSV’s physical benefits, particularly regarding joint mobility, strength, enhancement.

Table : 01
Basic movement of the upper and lower limbs

Name of the movements	Define the movements	Examples of bones	Examples of muscles	Sources (ref.)
Flexion	Decreasing the angle between two body parts	Upper Limb: Elbow joint	Upper Limb: Biceps brachii, brachial	Kaminoff & Matthews; (2012) Tortora & Derrickson (2015)
		Lower Limb: Knee joint, hip joint	Lower Limb: Hamstrings (biceps femurs, semitendinosus, semimembranosus)	
Extension	Increasing the angle between two body parts	Upper Limb: Triceps brachii	Upper Limb: Elbow joint	Kaminoff & Matthews; (2012) Tortora & Derrickson (2015)
		Lower Limb: Quadriceps (rectus femurs, vastus lateralize, vastus medialis, vastus inter medius)	Lower Limb: Knee joint, hip joint	
Abduction	Moving away from the midline	Upper Limb: Deltoid, supraspinatus	Upper Limb: Shoulder joint	Kaminoff & Matthews; (2012) Tortora & Derrickson (2015)
		Lower Limb: Gluteus medius, gluteus minimus	Lower Limb: Hip joint	
Adduction	Moving towards the midline	Upper Limb: Latissimus dorsi, pectoralis major	Upper Limb: Shoulder joint	Kaminoff & Matthews; (2012) Tortora & Derrickson (2015)
		Lower Limb: Adductors (adductor longus, adductor magnus, adductor brevis)	Lower Limb: Hip joint	
Internal Rotation	Turning inward toward the midline	Upper Limb: Subscapularis, pectoralis major	Upper Limb: Shoulder joint	Kaminoff & Matthews; (2012) Tortora & Derrickson (2015)
		Lower Limb: Tensor fasciae latae, gluteus medius	Lower Limb: Hip joint	
External Rotation		Upper Limb: Subscapularis, pectoralis major	Upper Limb: Shoulder joint	

	Turning outward away from the midline	Lower Limb: Tensor fasciae latae, gluteus medius	Lower Limb: Hip joint	Kaminoff & Matthews; (2012) Tortora & Derrickson (2015)
Inversion	Turning the sole of the foot inward	Lower Limb: Tibia anterior, tibia posterior	Lower Limb: Ankle joint (subtalar and talocrural joints)	Tortora & Derrickson (2015)
Everson	Turning the sole of the foot outward	Lower Limb: Peroneus longus, peroneus brevis	Lower Limb: Ankle joint (subtalar and talocrural joints)	Tortora & Derrickson (2015)

Table: 02
Upper and Lower Limb Sukshma Vyayama exercises
according to Kaminoff & Matthews (2012) and (Tortora & Derrickson (2015),
highlighting the joints and muscles.

Types of practices		Joints work	Muscles work
Upper limbs			
1.	Yogic Prarthana	Shoulder joint – glenohumeral joint Elbow joint – Humeroradial (Radioulnar) joint	Deltoids, Triceps, Biceps
2.	Skandhatatha Bahu-mula-sakti-vikasaka	Shoulder (Glenohumeral), Scapulothoracic	Deltoids, Rotator Cuff (Supraspinatus, Infraspinatus, Subscapularis)
3.	Bhuja-bandha-sakti-vikasaka	Elbow (Humeroulnar)	Biceps Brachii, Brachialis
4.	Kaphoni-sakti-vikasaka	Elbow (Humeroulnar, Humeroradial)	Brachioradialis, Triceps
5.	Bhuja-balli-sakti-vikasaka	Shoulder, Elbow, Wrist (Radio carpal)	Biceps, Triceps, Forearm Flexors and Extensors
6.	Purna-bhuja sakti-vikasaka	Shoulder, Elbow, Wrist	Deltoids, Biceps, Triceps, Wrist Flexors and Extensors
7.	Mani-bandha-sakti-vikasaka	Wrist (Radio carpal)	Forearm Flexors, Extensors (Flexor Carpi Ulna, Extensor Carpi Radial)
8.	Kara-prstha-sakti-vikasaka	Wrist, Metacarpophalangeal	Extensor Digitorum, Extensor Carpi Radial
9.	Kara-tala-sakti-vikasaka	Wrist, Metacarpophalangeal	Palmaris Longus, Flexor Digitorum
10.	Angula-mula-sakthi-vikasaka	Metacarpophalangeal (Finger Joints)	Flexor Digitorum Superficialis, Lumbricals
11.	Anguli -sakti-vikasaka	Interphalangeal Joints	Flexor and Extensor Digitorum
Lower limbs			
1	Jangha-Sakti-Vikasaka [1]	Hip (Acetabulofemoral)	Quadriceps, Hamstrings
2	Jangha-Sakti-Vikasaka [2]	Hip, Knee (Tibio femoral)	Gluteus Maximus, Quadriceps, Hamstring
3	Janu-Sakti-Vikasaka	Knee (Tibiofemoral)	Quadriceps, Hamstrings
4	Pindali-Sakti-Vikasaka	Ankle (Talocrural)	Gastrocnemius, Soleus
5	Pada-mula-sakti	Foot (Tarsometatarsal, Metatarsophalangeal)	Intrinsic Foot Muscles, Flexor Hallucis Longus
6	Gulpha-Pada-Prstha-Pada-tala-Sakti-Vikasaka	Ankle, Foot	Tibialis Anterior, Peroneus Longus, Flexor Digitorum longus.

Table 03: Literature Review

Sl	Author (Year)	Title of the study	Study design	No. of participants (Age range)	Intervention(s)	Assessments	Outcomes
1.	Skultetyova, D., et al., (2019)	Influence of power yoga on the explosive strength of upper and lower limbs and heart performance of dancers	Experimental study with control and experimental groups	16 dancers (main age category) 8 in the experimental group and 8 in the control group	Experimental group: 8-week power yoga training program, twice a week for 60 minutes. Control group: continued with regular dance training.	Input measurements before the 8-week training; output measurements after the training	Focused on improving phasic muscle strength, stretching postural muscles, enhancing cardiovascular and respiratory systems, and reducing stress to influence dance performance.
2.	Chelly, M.S., et al., (2010)	Relationships Between Power and Strength of the Upper and Lower Limb Muscles and Throwing Velocity in Male Handball Players	Correlational study	14 male handball players (age: 19.6 ± 0.6 years)	Not applicable (observational study focusing on relationships between strength/power measures and performance).	Upper and lower limb force-velocity tests using a modified Monark cycle ergometer to measure peak power (PP) and maximal force (F0) and velocity (V0). Maximal upper limb strength via 1RM bench press and pullover exercises. Muscle volume estimated with anthropometric methods. Throwing velocity (T3-Steps) assessed using radar Stalker ATS system.	Improved throwing velocity with strength training
3.	Abdalla, P. P., et al., (2021)	Identification of Muscle Weakness in Older Adults from Normalized Upper and Lower Limbs Strength: A Cross-Sectional Study	Cross-sectional study	94 community-dwelling older adults (≥60 years; 69.1% women)	No intervention; analysis of muscle strength normalized by body size.	1 handgrip strength (1IGS), 1RM for knee extensors, isokinetic knee extension peak torque (PT), six-minute walk test (6MWT)	Normalized strength improves detection of muscle weakness.
4.	Kaur, H., et al., (2023)	Core Strength as a Paramount Contributor for Potential Upper Limb Isometric Strength - A Correlational Study	Correlational study	67 female athletes; 60 female overhead athletes (18-25 years)	No intervention (observational study)	Isometric push-up/pull-down strength, abdominal and back strength	Core strength influences upper limb isometric strength
5	Liu, A. M., et al., (2021)	Training Benefits and Injury Risks of Standing Yoga Applied in Musculoskeletal Problems: Lower Limb Biomechanical Analysis	Biomechanical Analysis	11 female yoga instructors (. Average age: 40.7 years ± 6.0 years)	Five standing yoga poses (Chair, Tree, Warrior 1, 2, 3)	Electromyography (EMG) for muscle activity, joint moments of force (JMOFs) using motion capture system and ground reaction force platform, data synchronized for kinematic analysis.	Significant differences in hip, knee, and ankle JMOFs; Chair pose had the highest rectus femoris activation; Warrior 2 had the highest vastus lateralis activation; Warrior 1 had the highest vastus medialis activation; Warrior 3 beneficial for hamstring rehabilitation; Tree pose beneficial for beginners with low stability.
6	Gothe, N. P., et al., (2016)	Yoga is as Good as Stretching-Strengthening Exercises in Improving Functional Fitness Outcomes: Results From a Randomized Controlled Trial	Randomized Controlled Trial (RCTs)	N = 118 (55-79 years)	8-week Hatha yoga vs. stretching-strengthening exercises, 3x/week	Balance, strength, flexibility, mobility tests	Yoga equally effective as stretching-strengthening exercises.

7	Bartolomei et al. (2018)	Effect of Lower-Body Resistance Training on Upper-Body Strength Adaptation in Trained Men	Randomized Controlled Trial	N = 20 (24.9 ± 2.9 to 26.0 ± 4.7 years)	High-intensity (HI) training vs. Mixed high-volume and HI (MF) training	Maximal strength and power testing pre- and post-training	MP group showed greater upper-body strength gains
8	Kang Hye Cho et al. (2012)	Effect of Lower Limb Strength on Falls and Balance of the Elderly	Observational Study	86 (69.8 ± 5.3 years)	None (Evaluation study)	Chair stand test, Stability index (Balance System SD)	Lower limb strength correlates with fall risk and balance.
9	Michael O. Harris-Love et al., (2018)	The Influence of Upper and Lower Extremity Strength on Performance-Based Sarcopenia Assessment Tests	Prospective Clinical Trial	30 (45-83 years)	None (Strength assessment study)	Hand grip force, Knee extensor/flexor torque, Gait speed, Sit-to-stand, PPT-7	Lower extremity strength correlated with functional performance.
10.	Bartolomei, S, et al.,(2018)	Effect of Lower-Body Resistance Training on Upper-Body Strength Adaptation in Trained Men	Randomized controlled trial	20 Trained men (18-35 years)	6-week HI vs. mixed high-volume & HI program	Body composition, 1RM bench press, power testing	MP group showed greater upper body strength gains
11.	Desrosiers, J., et al.,(2005)	Validation of a New Lower-Extremity Motor Coordination Test	Reliability and construct validity study	29 (28-87 years) for reliability; 144 post-stroke for validity	Not applicable (evaluating a new test)	LEMOCOT, Fughl-Meyer Assessment, Berg Balance Scale, 5-m and 2-min walking tests, Functional Autonomy Measurement, Modified Mini-Mental State, Motor-Free Visual Perceptual Test	LEMOCOT showed good reliability and construct validity
12.	Togawat, K, et al.,(2024)	Randomized controlled trial investigating the role of yoga at workplace in improving fatigue, burnout, pain, strength, and quality of life among blue-collar workers	Randomized controlled trial (RCT)	128 (25-50 years)	40 minutes daily supervised yoga-based loosening exercises (YLE), 5 days/week for 1 month, followed by 1 month of unsupervised home practice	Chalder Fatigue Scale (CFS), Visual Analog Scale for pain, Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI), sit-and-reach test (SRT), handgrip strength dynamometer, Short Form-8 (SF-8) questionnaire	Significant reduction in fatigue, pain, burnout; improved flexibility, strength, quality of life
13	Smets, M. P., et al.,(2009)	Constrained handgrip force decreases upper extremity muscle activation and arm strength	Experimental study	10 healthy right-handed females (age not specified)	Specified (30% maximum voluntary grip) and preferred grip forces during maximal arm exertions	Electromyography for muscle activity, maximal arm force measurements across 5 directions and 2 heights	Reduced arm strength and muscle activation with constrained grip
14	Au, A. K., et al.,(2007)	Interfering effects of multitasking on muscle activity in the upper extremity	Experimental study	16 healthy 8 male and 8 female participants (Mean age: 25.1 years)	Simultaneous hand and shoulder exertions with 4 grip conditions, 3 shoulder conditions, and a mental task (Stroop test).	Surface electromyography (EMG) for muscle activity, grip and shoulder force measurements, Stroop test performance	Increased muscle load with multitasking conditions

Discussion:

Yogic Sukshma Vyayama (YSV) is an age-old technique that strengthens muscles and increases mobility through delicate, precise body movements. Every area of the body, from head to toe, is targeted by these 48 motions, which Brahmachari outlined in 1980. People of all ages can benefit greatly from them. YSV is easy to do, equipment-free, and suitable for daily use. Schools, senior living facilities, and rehabilitation centre all use it. It enhances flexibility and muscle function, according to studies. According to (Bhowmik Bhunia et al., 2024), for instance, YSV improved muscle control in those with vocal issues (Nayak et al., 2024). Showed that specific YSV exercises reduced neck stiffness. For upper body strength, (Gawel et al., 2024). Observed increased grip and shoulder strength after yoga practice (Lambert et al., 2019). also found that yoga improved bone health and muscle density in young women (Skultetyova et al., 2019; Cramer et al., 2016). Showed that similar yoga styles helped improve both arm and leg strength and balance. For older adults, maintaining muscle is important. Sarcopenia, or age-related muscle loss, reduces movement and increases the risk of falls (Park et al., 2024). Showed that YSV helps prevent these problems (Hermann et al., 2005). also found that arm and leg strength are closely related, meaning that whole-body exercises like YSV are especially useful. However, most of the available research studies broader yoga practices, not just YSV. More high-quality research is needed using advanced tools like EMG (to study muscle activity) or long-term testing. It would also help to compare YSV with traditional strength training to find where it works best. In short, YSV is a practical, full-body exercise system that strengthens limbs and improves balance, posture, and flexibility. It holds great promise in modern health and wellness.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the collection of studies illustrates the multifaceted benefits of various exercise regimens such as power yoga, resistance training, and core strengthening on upper and lower limb strength, core stability, and overall physical performance. From dancers and athletes to older adults and workers, these exercises demonstrate their effectiveness in enhancing strength, balance, cardiovascular health, and injury prevention. Power yoga, for example, proves to be a valuable tool for improving explosive strength and endurance, while resistance training shows the interconnectedness between upper and lower body muscles. Furthermore, the studies emphasize core strength's essential role in supporting upper limb functionality and the importance of lower limb strength in preventing falls in older populations. Ultimately, these findings promote a holistic approach to fitness, applicable to diverse populations and tailored to their unique physical needs.

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